

**Nature's Navigation: Biomimetic Insights from Slime Mold Networks
for Optimizing the Translink SkyTrain System**

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Summative Report on Biomimetic Applications

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Author Note

Special Thanks to Mr. Terence Wong for his Influence on our Collaboration.

This is from the previous knowledge gained in class for our Inspiration from Nature.

Introduction

What the essence of this Project is about:

As for the creation of this “Biomimetic Applications Summative Report,” it can be said that Biomimicry offers a fascinating approach to innovation, drawing inspiration from nature's enduring solutions to tackle human challenges sustainably. According to the Biomimicry Institute (2024), Biomimicry can be defined as “an approach to innovation that seeks sustainable solutions to human challenges by emulating nature’s time-tested patterns and strategies.” It is with the goal to create products, processes, and policies, as a new way of living that is well-adapted to life on earth over the long haul (Biomimicry Institute, 2024). Through billions of years of evolution, Nature has honed efficient solutions to a wide array of challenges. Seen with Animals, plants, and even microscopic organisms, which have adapted and optimized their structures and functions to thrive in their environments. Janine Benyus, a pioneering biologist in biomimicry, famously stated that "Nature has already solved all the challenges we face. Failures have become fossils, and what surrounds us holds the key to survival." Her insights emphasize the potential of mimicking nature's strategies in human innovation (Benyus, 2019).

Figure 1: Inside of a Nautilus
Sourced from Unsplash.com

What aspect of our daily lives does this involve?

The TransLink SkyTrain system in Metro Vancouver exemplifies the vital role of rapid transit in urban mobility. As Vancouver's population grows, so does the demand on the SkyTrain, leading to issues like overcrowding and operational inefficiencies. In an article, Mackle (2024) comments it took 25 years to reach three million with B.C. Stats projects Metro will hit four million in 2041, which is in 17 years. Addressing these challenges is crucial not only for improving

Figure 2: Skytrain on Route
Sourced from Progressive Railroading

commuter experience but also for fostering sustainable urban development. This project, titled "Nature's Navigation: Biomimetic Insights from Natural Networks for Optimizing the Translink SkyTrain System," explores how principles observed in natural systems can enhance the efficiency of the SkyTrain network. By studying natural network

formation strategies, we aim to discover innovative approaches to reduce congestion, improve connectivity, and promote sustainable transit solutions. By integrating biological insights with engineering principles, our study aims to bridge the gap between natural phenomena and human-made systems. From which, we aspire to contribute to the development of a more resilient and efficient public transit infrastructure that meets the evolving needs of Greater Vancouver Area.

Background Information

What is Rapid Transit?

Rapid transit, otherwise known as mass rapid transit (MRT), commonly referred to as metro, is a type of high-capacity public transport that is generally built in urban areas. It is seen through a grade-separated rapid transit line below ground surface through a tunnel, regionally called a subway, tube, or underground, however, they are also seen on elevated platforms (T. Editors of Encyclopedia, 2024). Unlike buses or trams, Rapid Transit Systems consist of railways, usually electric, that operate on an exclusive right-of-way, which cannot be accessed by pedestrians or other vehicles (T. Editors of Encyclopedia, 2024).

Figure 3: Skytrain on Route
Sourced from CTV News Vancouver

What is the TransLink SkyTrain System?

The SkyTrain is a medium-capacity rapid transit system serving the Metro Vancouver region in British Columbia, Canada. (Wikipedia, 2024). It consists of 79.6 km of track and uses fully automated trains on grade-separated tracks running on underground and elevated guideways. It is the longest rapid transit system in Canada and the longest fully automated driverless system in the world. (Wikipedia, 2024). SkyTrain has 53 stations served by three lines: the Expo Line, the

Millennium Line, and the Canada Line. This system is vital for daily commuters, providing a reliable and efficient means of transportation across the region, serving as an integral part of Greater Vancouver's public transportation network. It facilitates the movement of thousands of people daily, reducing the dependence on personal vehicles and helping to alleviate traffic congestion. Ridership on SkyTrain's combined Expo and Millennium lines reached 83 million in 2022 with averages of

Figure 4: Skytrain Map of Current Lines
Sourced from Translink Website

252,000 boardings per weekday and 151,000 per Sunday (Chan, 2024). It is also essential for connecting various parts of the metropolitan area, making it easier for residents to access jobs, education, and other essential services. As Vancouver continues to grow, the SkyTrain system's role in providing efficient and sustainable transportation becomes increasingly important. As said by Honourable Justin Trudeau, Prime Minister of Canada, “By continuing to invest in major public transit projects, we’re shortening commutes, creating well-paying, middle class jobs, growing the economy.”

What are the recent and planned expansions of the TransLink SkyTrain system in Greater Vancouver?

Recent expansions of the TransLink SkyTrain system have been worthwhile over the past couple of decades which showcase the growth the Lower Mainland has had. This can be seen in

the TransLink SkyTrain system, including the Evergreen Extension, which is a 10.9-kilometre-long (6.8 mi) extension of the Millennium Line connecting Coquitlam and Port Moody completed in 2016 (Wikipedia, 2024). This extension has improved connectivity for the Tri-Cities area, making it easier for residents to commute to and from downtown Vancouver and other key areas. Seen throughout the Lower Mainland, the travel time from the Millennium's

Figure 5: Skytrain Map of Surrey-Langley Extension Sourced from Translink Website

Vancouver terminus to the new Coquitlam terminus is 36 minutes, which is highly competitive to trips performed by vehicle during most times of the day (Chan, 2016). To continue, the planned Surrey-Langley SkyTrain extension is set to expand the Expo Line, adding several new stations and extending the reach into the Fraser Valley, known as one of the fastest growing areas in the region (Government of British Columbia, 2024). The business case estimate for the total cost of Surrey Langley SkyTrain is \$4.01 billion, which includes capital costs and active transportation investments (Government of British Columbia, 2024). This project aims to improve transportation options for residents of Surrey and Langley, two of the fastest-growing areas in Greater Vancouver. To continue, the Broadway Subway Project, a 5.7-kilometre line will extend the existing Millennium Line from VCC-Clark Station to a new terminus station at Arbutus Street (Transportation Investment Corporation, 2019). These expansions are part of a broader vision to

Figure 6: Skytrain Map of Broadway Subway Project Sourced from Translink Website

enhance the public transit network, making it more accessible and efficient for residents and visitors. The projects are expected to significantly improve the overall transportation infrastructure, supporting economic growth and development in the region. Seen by a comment made by Professor Santa J. Ono, President and Vice-Chancellor of UBC Business in Vancouver, “Extending the Millennium Line SkyTrain to UBC will contribute to a growing transit network that meets the needs of the entire region, reducing congestion, moving people more quickly and safely between their homes and places of work” (University of British Columbia, 2024).

Goals of the Expansion:

With the primary goals of the SkyTrain expansion including reducing traffic congestion, improving regional connectivity, and supporting sustainable urban development. As said Sany Zein, President and General Manager of BC Rapid Transit Company during an interview with Daily Hive Urbanized, he comments “I believe we are embarking on the most exciting time for public transit expansion in this region” (Chan, 22). TransLink aims to provide a reliable and efficient transportation option that can accommodate the growing population of Greater Vancouver. Looking at a specific example, The Surrey Langley SkyTrain will improve the

Figure 7: Population Projection of Metro Vancouver Sourced from Daily Hive

transportation experience, increase access to opportunities and housing, support healthy communities and environment, and support economic development (Government of Canada, 2024). The expansion also seeks to promote transit-oriented development, which can lead to more vibrant and livable communities. Additionally, reducing the reliance on personal vehicles through improved public transit can contribute to environmental sustainability by lowering greenhouse gas emissions. For instance, seen in the current Evergreen Extension of the Millennium Line, the travel time from the Millennium's Vancouver terminus to the Coquitlam terminus is 36 minutes, being highly competitive to trips performed by vehicle during most times of the day (Chan, 2016).

Question or Problem:

Question:

How can the TransLink SkyTrain system in the Lower Mainland of British Columbia be optimized to efficiently accommodate the region's growing population and mitigate the challenges of overcrowding?

Figure 8: Peak Hour Image in Stadium-Chinatown Subway Station
Sourced from Daily Hive

The Problem being faced by the TransLink SkyTrain System:

The problem we are addressing is the inefficiency and overcrowding of the TransLink SkyTrain system in the Lower Mainland of British Columbia. While the current system functions adequately, it struggles to meet the demands of a rapidly growing population. British Columbia, a fast-growing province, attracts many new residents each year. In areas such as Surrey and Langley, the number of riders has doubled over the past four years, according to TransLink (Hamilton,

2023). This surge has led to busy and crowded SkyTrain stations, especially during peak hours, causing discomfort and delays for commuters. In response to this issue, our group aims to explore ways to create a more efficient system that would reduce crowding and enhance the overall commuting experience.

Significance of the Problem:

Overcrowding in the SkyTrain system is not merely an inconvenience; it poses significant challenges for both daily commuters and the broader transportation network. Overcrowded trains can lead to longer wait times, reduced passenger comfort, and increased likelihood of delays and service disruptions. Moreover, it can deter potential riders from using public transit, leading to higher car usage, increased traffic congestion, and elevated greenhouse gas emissions. The human problem at the core of this issue is the daily struggle of commuters who rely on the SkyTrain for their

Figure 9: Peak Hour Image at UBC Rapid Bus
Sourced from Translink

transportation needs. Overcrowded trains often mean that passengers are forced to stand in tightly packed spaces, sometimes unable to board due to lack of space. This can be particularly problematic during inclement weather, peak travel times, and for individuals with mobility challenges. Addressing this issue is crucial for improving the quality of life for Metro Vancouver residents and ensuring a sustainable and efficient transportation system.

Relevant News and Recent Developments:

In June 2024, TransLink announced its 2024 Investment Plan aimed at addressing critical overcrowding issues on the SkyTrain system. This plan includes several key improvements, such as increasing service on 60 bus routes, extending evening hours on 11 bus routes, expanding the bus fleet, and increasing Canada Line frequencies (Mall, 2024).

Figure 10: Picture depicting Train car on Canada Line
Sourced from Wikipedia

Additionally, TransLink plans to order 100 new generation SkyTrain cars by 2024 to provide much-needed relief to the overcrowded Expo and Millennium Lines. These new cars will feature more spacious interiors, efficient seating layouts, and improved lighting and design to enhance passenger comfort (Chan, 2017). These initiatives are part of a broader strategy to keep up with Metro Vancouver's unprecedented population growth and ensure the transit system can accommodate future demand. The Mayors' Council and TransLink's Board of Directors are also working on a 2025 Investment Plan to develop a long-term funding model for sustainable transit growth in the region. According to the Indo-Canadian Voice, this comprehensive approach is crucial to addressing both short-term and long-term challenges posed by rapid urban growth.

A news report from CTV News further highlights the importance of these investments. It quotes TransLink CEO Kevin Quinn, who emphasizes the critical need for continuous improvement and expansion of the transit network to meet the growing demands. Quinn mentions that without these upgrades, the system risks becoming increasingly unreliable and inefficient,

which could have severe implications for the region’s mobility and economic health. Moreover, the provincial government’s involvement is significant. In addition to the \$300 million in capital funding from the Government of British Columbia, the 2025 Investment Plan saw historic investments amounting to \$479 million to support the transit system during the pandemic and ensure its recovery. Transportation and Infrastructure Minister Rob Fleming highlighted that these investments are pivotal for the continued expansion and improvement of transit services, ensuring they can meet the needs of Metro Vancouver's rapidly expanding population.

Implementing this using our own Data:

To gather information and understand the real-life impacts of the current system, we conducted interviews with regular SkyTrain users at Surrey Central Sky Station. These interviews provided valuable insights into the problems faced by daily commuters and highlighted areas that need improvement. This feedback was essential for developing solutions that can better serve the growing population and make the SkyTrain system more efficient and user-friendly. After conducting interviews with nine individuals, we found that 22.2% (2 people) expressed dissatisfaction with the system, while 33.3% (3 people) viewed it positively, and 44.4% (4 people) regarded it as acceptable or satisfactory. While these results indicate a generally neutral to positive

Pie Chart 1: Community's Opinion on Skytrain System

Created using Excel with Collected Data

sentiment towards the SkyTrain system, we also inquired about the aspects that users found most challenging and most commendable. Below are the detailed findings:

After soliciting opinions on the SkyTrain system's drawbacks, 11.1% (1 person) cited slow train frequency, another 11.1% (1 person) mentioned uncomfortable seats in older models, and 11.1% (1 person) was unsure. Interestingly, 22.2% (2 people) reported no specific issues with the system, while a significant 44.4% (4 people) highlighted overcrowding and overpopulation as major concerns. Regarding the system's strengths, 11.1% (1 person) appreciated its performance during off-peak hours, another 11.1% (1 person) liked that it operates above ground, and a further 11.1% (1 person) praised its accessibility. Additionally, 22.2% (2 people) commended its reliability and maintenance, and 33.3% noted its efficiency in terms of frequency, time-saving capabilities, and overall convenience.

Negative aspects about the Skytrain System

- Slow Train Frequency
- Uncomfortable Seats
- Unsure
- No Issues
- Overpopulated/ Crowdiness

Pie Chart 2: Negative Aspects about the Skytrain System
Created using Excel with Collected Data

Positive aspects about the Skytrain System

- Availability during Off Peak Hours
- Above Ground Level
- Accessibility
- Reliability and Maintenance
- Efficiency, Time-Saving Capabilities, Overall Convenience

Pie Chart 3: Positive Aspects about the Skytrain System
Created using Excel with Collected Data

Having done that, we collected the data and input it into a pie chart using Excel. This was done by Djaurv, as with this being conducted by Tejvir, When asked for suggestions on how to improve the system, respondents provided the following feedback:

The results show that 11.1% (1 person) of people want to improve the Millennium line, 11.1% (1 person) want to reduce littering, 22.2% (2 people) want to hire more, passionate employees, and 55.6% (5 people) want more skytrains and want to expand the system.

After analyzing the data collected, it is evident that overcrowding and overpopulation pose significant challenges for the SkyTrain system in British Columbia. With the province experiencing steady growth driven by immigration, the current system is struggling to meet the increasing demand for efficient transportation. As seen in an article by Yu (2024), the Growth was driven by an increase in net non-permanent residents. Net non-permanent residents in Vancouver reached 92,529 people in the 2022-23 period, compared to just over 24,000 in the prior period (Yu, 2024). As a result, many newcomers as well as preexisting Transit Users, rely on public transit to access housing, job opportunities, educational institutions, and essential services. The solution

lies in expanding the SkyTrain network and increasing the number of trains to alleviate congestion. The SkyTrain system is a vital part of public transportation in the Lower Mainland, providing a fast and efficient way for commuters to travel. As the population continues to grow, the demand for public transportation will increase. Many immigrants and residents do not own cars and rely on the

Figure 11: Picture depicting Immigration by City Sourced from Statistics Canada

SkyTrain to get to work, school, and other important places. Without an expanded SkyTrain system, these individuals may face significant challenges in their daily commutes, leading to increased reliance on personal vehicles, higher traffic congestion, and greater environmental impact. Having said that, as Don Luymes, general manager for planning and development for the City of Surrey for the Surrey Langley SkyTrain extension project, once said, “When you get a major rapid transit line coming in like that, it certainly does adjust how we expect the population [to grow] around the region” (Denner, 2023). As an example seen, the Surrey Langley SkyTrain would cover 25 per cent of the population of Metro Vancouver, it will help improve public transit accessibility for residents and businesses south of the Fraser River, connect more people to housing, employment, and schools, and encourage greater

Figure 12: Photo showcasing the construction of the Broadway Subway Plan Sourced from Vancouver is Awesome

development around SkyTrain stations (City of Surrey, 2021). In correlation to this, building SkyTrain along the Broadway corridor all the way to UBC will provide for new opportunities for densification and much-needed new housing. (Antweiler, 2019). With British Columbia facing issues related to overpopulation, ensuring a robust transportation infrastructure extends upon this. Unlike more densely populated countries like the U.S. and U.K., Canada has the advantage of land availability, but effective public transit remains essential for sustainable urban development. With that said, we can also see that the current system is not too efficient as it does not cover many important areas such as the University of British Columbia, for this is crucial for an expansion of the Skytrain System would be very beneficial for many people, in particular students. According to UBC (n.d) in 2021, Translink surveyed more than 15,000 people all over Vancouver on a possible

Figure 13: Picture of the University of British Columbia
Sourced from University of British Columbia

UBC expansion and 92% of people were in support of this expansion. They also asked people who didn't live in Vancouver and left further away from UBC and that survey resulted in 93% of people being in support of this, as it's clear that enhancing the SkyTrain system is a priority shared by many. An expanded SkyTrain system would not only reduce overcrowding but also improve overall accessibility and connectivity within the region. By increasing the number of trains and extending the network to underserved areas, we can create a more resilient and adaptable transportation system that meets the needs of a growing population. Moreover, a well-maintained and efficient SkyTrain system can encourage more people to use public transportation, reducing

the reliance on cars and contributing to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly urban environment. If we do not address the issue of overcrowding and inefficiency in the SkyTrain system, it will become a significant problem for British Columbia in the coming years. As the population continues to grow, the existing infrastructure will struggle to keep up with demand, leading to increased congestion, longer travel times, and a decline in the quality of service. Expanding the SkyTrain system is a proactive measure that can ensure the region's public transportation network remains robust and capable of supporting the needs of its residents now and in the future.

Inspiration from Nature:

The Inspiration behind our Biomimicry Project, sparking a change:

Inspired by innovation acquired from the natural world, the both of us, Tejvir and Djaury, came up with the solution to our problem for the improvement of the overcrowding issue seen in the preexisting Skytrain system. Our inspiration from nature had come from the fascinating organism being *Physarum polycephalum*, commonly known as the slime mold, optimizing resource distribution and navigating complex environments. From that, it could be mentioned that Slime molds are unique organisms belonging to the kingdom Protista, known for being

Figure 14: Slime Mold seen on Leaves
Sourced from Wired

either a unicellular or multicellular creature which thrives without a brain and contains multiple nuclei. Umedachi et al. (2013) touches upon this, explaining how *Physarum polycephalum* is an amoeba-like unicellular organism that does not possess any nervous system or specialized organs for it has no “brain,” however, this does not mean it is not a highly intelligent creature.

Background and Details about Slime Mold:

An aspect of slime molds can be perceived from their ability to form intricate networks of interconnected tubes, seen as veins called "pseudopodia." Pseudopodia are extensions of the cell membrane and cytoplasm used by slime molds like *Physarum polycephalum* for movement and nutrient acquisition. These structures are integral to the slime mold's ability to navigate its environment and distribute nutrients efficiently. Mentioned by the University of Toronto (2022), this single-celled amoeboid organism grows as a greenish-yellow system of veins, forming tubular network that is optimized to transfer nutrients

Figure 15: Slime Mold seen on Decaying Wood
Sourced from Orillia Matters

efficiently throughout the entire organism. These networks allow them to navigate their environment by “foraging” over an area, then refining their tubular network to optimize for the distribution of the nutrients effectively. It develops as a vascular network of protoplasm, which is the living content of the cell surrounded by a plasma membrane, including the cytoplasm, nucleus, and other organelles within the cell. The organism first establishes a dense and continuous mesh, reinforcing optimal pathways over time through constructive feedbacks of protoplasmic streaming. (Kay, Raphael, et al., 2022).

Why does your Inspiration need to do this?

Having said that, slime molds can solve complex spatial problems, such as finding the shortest path between food sources, without any central coordination. They achieve this through a process known as "chemotaxis," having individual cells communicate and coordinate their movements based on chemical signals. As such, the main aspect that will be primarily focused on is the process of how the slime mold finds and consumes its nutrients to sustain life. This ability to form efficient networks and navigate complex environments without central control is essential

Figure 16: Slime Mold showcasing “Networks”
Sourced from Scott Chimileski

for the slime mold's survival. It ensures that the organism can efficiently find and distribute nutrients, thereby sustaining its growth and development. In their natural habitats, slime molds must navigate through soil, decaying wood, and other substrates to locate food sources like bacteria, fungi, and other organic matter. Their ability to form an optimized network of pseudopodia allows them to cover large areas and transport nutrients effectively. This network formation is crucial for their survival, enabling them to thrive in diverse and often challenging environments.

How does Nature use it or do with it? How does it work?

In Slime Molds, protoplasm in a slime mold can be compared to the train cars and passengers of a Skytrain system, carrying essential nutrients and organelles needed for cellular functions. Pseudopodia, on the other hand, are like the tracks of the Skytrain system, extending outward to create pathways for the protoplasm to flow. Just as the movement of trains on the tracks ensures efficient transport of passengers throughout the city, the flow of protoplasm within the pseudopodia ensures that nutrients are distributed efficiently throughout the slime mold.

Figure 17: Translink Skytrain Car being Transported
Sourced from The Buzzed Blog

Slime molds can solve complex spatial problems, such as finding the shortest path between food sources, without any central coordination. They achieve this through a process known as "chemotaxis," where individual cells communicate and coordinate their movements based on chemical signals.

Applying Nature's Efficiency to the Skytrain System:

Drawing inspiration from slime mold's efficient nutrient distribution networks, we propose applying similar principles to enhance the Skytrain system. By mimicking slime molds' pseudopodia networks, we can optimize the Skytrain's route planning and resource allocation. This approach could dynamically adjust train schedules and routes, alleviating congestion and improving overall efficiency. Implementing these decision-making mechanisms similar to that of the slime mold's chemotaxis could enable the system to autonomously adapt to changing passenger flows, ensuring smoother operations and enhanced commuter experience. This biomimetic approach not only addresses the current issues of overcrowding and inefficiency but also provides a scalable solution that can adapt to future growth and demand. By looking to nature, we can find sustainable and innovative ways to improve our public transportation systems, ultimately benefiting the entire community.

Figure 18: Translink Rapid Transit Plan 2050
Sourced from Translink

What this done previously?

With this being done similarly to a Japanese laboratory on a study for better network design through biological principles, the correlation of this deals with the rapidly produced a web of slimy tubes that looks similar to Tokyo's actual railway network. Noting such from coauthor Mark Fricker of the University of Oxford, he states, "In contrast, the slime mold has no central brain or indeed any awareness of the overall problem it is trying to solve, but manages to produce a

structure with similar properties to the real rail network" (Sanders, 2010). From how Yong (2010) mentions that the point of this isn't to reconstruct the monster attacks of the Slime mold culture, rather, to find ways of improving transport networks by recruiting nature as a town planner. With that, it can be mentioned how human societies depend on good

Figure 19: Study done in Tokyo Network Formation
Sourced from Research Gate

transport networks for the allocation of individuals, resources and information from place to place, but setting up such networks isn't an easy task. They have to be efficient, cost-effective and resistant to interruptions or failure. Drawing inspiration from these biological networks, Atsushi Tero from Hokkaido University worked with the slime mold, *Physarum polycephalum*, as this amoeba-like creature forages for food by sending out branches plasmodia from a central location (Yong, 2010). From the sight of various veins change thickness and shape, as the entire network

crawls a few centimetres every hour, it is an impressive sight on how a mindless organism, the slime mold, creating efficient networks. Inspired by these studies utilizing slime mold's natural network-building capabilities, there is potential seen in implementing similar principles in optimizing the Skytrain system in the Lower Mainland. By leveraging decentralized, self-organizing strategies akin to slime mold's pseudopodia networks, the Skytrain could dynamically adjust its routes and frequencies based on real-time passenger flow and demand. This could enhance operational efficiency, reduce congestion, and improve overall commuter experience. Like the slime mold's ability to adapt and optimize its network without central direction, integrating adaptive and decentralized controls into the Skytrain infrastructure could lead to a more resilient and responsive transit system. Such innovations could revolutionize urban transit planning by utilizing nature's efficiency and adaptability to meet the evolving needs of commuters in a bustling metropolitan area.

Figure 20: Tokyo Rail Network Formation with Lines

Sourced from Research Gate

Model of Our Solution

What did our Slime Mold and Skytrain System Model appear as?

Our approach to developing a more efficient Skytrain system is rooted in Biomimicry, drawing from inspiration seen by the remarkable behavior of Slime Mold. With that mentioned, Slime mold exhibits a sophisticated ability to navigate and optimize pathways between food sources. To replicate this biological innovation, we initiated our project by researching for an effective physical map of the Lower Mainland for our build. By doing so, Djaurv, I, was able to find a Map from the Article, “TransLink unveils first 10 years of Transport 2050 priorities” by Translink. As a result, the map served as the canvas upon which we would observe and simulate the growth patterns of slime mold. Key locations, such as major cities, densely populated areas, and crucial points of interest like universities and business hubs, were represented

Figure 21: Map showcasing areas of Mass Population Sourced from Translink

by strategically placed oats and water on the map. The initial step involved preparing the map, ensuring accuracy in geographical representation and scale in a 20cm by 30cm Plastic Container. Overlaying the map under with a thin layer of agar on the Plastic Container was the next step. From the Agar, seen as a gel-like substance derived from seaweed, provided a nutrient-rich environment conducive to slime mold growth. The agar layer mimicked the natural habitats where slime mold thrives, such as forest floors or decaying vegetation, facilitating the organism's natural tendencies to explore and establish efficient networks. Strategically placing oats and water on the

map simulated key locations and urban centers across the Lower Mainland. As the slime mold grew, it extended its network toward these food sources, organically creating paths that connected these important locations. These elements acted as attractants for the slime mold, prompting it to extend their “network” and form interconnected pathways. This initial setup was crucial for observing how slime mold naturally navigates terrain and optimizes routes for our transit planning model.

Figure 22: Original Draft of Design showcasing Initial Measurements, materials needed, Visuals from 3 Perspectives and Build creation.

Created by Djaurv through Freeform

Images of Appearance:

Figure 23, 24, & 25: Images showcasing our build model of the end result. Several images in different sides detailing what exactly is being shown.

Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab

Iterations and Development

Our project unfolded through several stages, each aimed at refining our understanding and application of slime mold behavior to transit planning. Each iteration allowed us to refine our understanding of how biological principles could inform urban transit design. Adjustments were made based on observed behaviors, ensuring that our model accurately reflected real-world transit challenges and opportunities. Transitioning from physical observation to digital analysis was a critical phase in our project's evolution. The initial prototype involved setting up the physical map with agar and monitoring the growth of slime mold over time, providing valuable insights into how natural

Figure 26: Close up image during Day two of Slime Mold growth
Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab

networks develop and adapt, optimizing for efficiency and resilience. As the slime mold expanded its network on the Agar, we documented and analyzed its growth patterns daily for 5 days. During the growth of our slime mold we had to make many changes to make sure that our slime mold would not die and provide us with a proper sky train system. During this experiment, we had given our slime mold oats and water so it would continue to grow every day. We would add the oats and water on top of the old oats that the slime mold had covered. To start, we decided to add oats in the important areas where there is overcrowding or areas that the current sky train doesn't even go to. We went with oats because oats were said have a lot of protein and nutrients (Davidoff and Rawshan, 2023). In addition to that, we provided it water, because Dr. Ong (2005) expressed Slime molds do not survive well in dry conditions. In relation, the optimal temperature for the Slime

Mold was anywhere from 70°F and 80°F, as we decided to go right in the middle and go for 75°F, storing our slime mold in an incubator which would help the Slime Mold grow in the optimal temperature (Flinn Scientific, 2016). The map plus the container representing the Lower Mainland, the oats represent densely populated areas, and the slime mold represents what the supposed

Figure 27: Photographed on Day four of our slime mold, growth, where new oats are seen added

Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab

Skytrain system will look like. In consideration of this, our design was not to exact scale, however we attempted our best, due to the limit in size, not going to fit into a container. Supposedly, the new Skytrain system is supposed to cover all of British Columbia, but of course, we couldn't realistically build, where we must use a website to demonstrate what our design would look like. To expand on this, it might be questioned of how we didn't have necessarily different iterations or models of our slime mold creation. In this project, we only had two, being the original depiction of our supposed plan implemented on "Freeform," an Apple iPad Exclusive App, as with the one we had created for our experimentation. We did not have different iterations due to our confidence in our model creation as to with having a solidified plan not requiring a change. This can be depicted from our original plan, being quite similar to the one that we had made.

Visual Representation and Analysis

Visual representation played a pivotal role in our project, offering clarity and insight into the complex interactions between biological principles and urban transit planning. Multiple angles and stages of our prototype and final model showcased its evolution, from the initial physical setup to the digital mapping and route optimization.

Photographs and diagrams captured the intricate growth patterns of slime mold on the agar-coated map.

These images illustrated how the organism naturally established efficient connections between simulated urban centers, highlighting the potential for biomimetic design in transit infrastructure. Observing these organic pathways provided evidence of nature's ability to solve complex spatial problems. Screenshots

Figure 28: Day three of our slime mold, growth, where new oats are seen added
Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab

from digital platforms like Felt.com depicted the overlay of slime mold-inspired routes onto digital maps of British Columbia. These visualizations demonstrated the practical application of our research, showing how biological principles could be translated into actionable transit solutions. Each visual representation served as a testament to the adaptability and scalability of our approach, emphasizing efficiency and sustainability in urban transportation design.

Figure 29: Image taken on Felt.com website implemented into a digital resource
Source is derived from Screenshots taken by Djaurv

Scale and Dimensions

Scale and dimensions were considered throughout our project to ensure accuracy and applicability in real-world scenarios. The initial physical map made was scaled at 1:300,000 with the actual map being approximately 60km in Length, providing a comprehensive view of the Lower Mainland's geographic landscape. This scale allowed us to simulate transit needs across diverse terrain and population centers, capturing the complexities of urban connectivity and mobility. Dimensions of the agar-coated map were tailored to accommodate the growth of slime mold and the placement of oats and water.

Figure 30: Image taken on Google Earth, depicting the length of the map in actuality
Source is derived from Screenshots taken by Djaurv

As for the pasta container with a lid, the dimensions were approximately 31.5cm x 20.2cm x 15.6cm. These elements were strategically positioned to simulate urban hubs and population clusters, reflecting the spatial dynamics that influence transit planning. Adjustments in scale and dimensions were informed by ongoing observations and analyses, ensuring that our model accurately represented the intricacies of transit infrastructure at various levels from local neighborhoods to regional networks.

Materials and Manufacturing Process

Key materials and the manufacturing process were integral to the success of our project, facilitating the integration of biological insights into urban transit planning. The choice of

materials for the map base ensured durability and accuracy in geographical representation. The agar provided a controlled environment for slime mold growth, replicating natural conditions conducive to network formation. The placement of oats and water on the agar-coated map simulated urban centers and landmarks critical for transit connectivity. These materials acted as attractants for slime mold, guiding its exploration and establishment of efficient pathways. Observational data collected during the growth phase informed subsequent iterations and adjustments, guiding the development of a robust transit planning model. Digital tools like Felt.com played a pivotal role in the digital conversion and visualization of biological networks. This platform enabled us to overlay slime mold-

Figure 31: Djaurv in Lab doing Daily Updates
Source is derived from Video,
Screenshotted by Djaurv

inspired routes onto digital maps, facilitating analysis and optimization of transit pathways. Collaboration with experts in biology, urban planning, and digital mapping enhanced the interdisciplinary nature of our approach, enriching the project with diverse perspectives and expertise.

Materials used during this project:

These were the items used during the Project:

- 1x Large plastic container with Lid (35cm x 20cm x 15cm)

A spacious container used as the primary vessel for conducting the experiment and housing the materials.

- 1x 50g Agar agar powder

A gelatinous substance used to make agar gel, which serves as a growth medium for cultivating microorganisms.

- 1x Print out of a map of Lower Mainland

A printed map used for geographical reference or for studying and mapping the distribution patterns of organisms.

- 1x 100g Oats

A food source provided for the slime mold to encourage growth and observe its feeding behavior.

- 1x 50mL Water and 1x Plastic Pipette

Essential for mixing solutions, preparing agar gel, and maintaining hydration for the experiment.

- 1x Bunsen Burner

A gas burner used for heating, and sterilization of items, requiring controlled high heat.

- 1x Striker

A tool used to safely ignite the Bunsen burner.

- 2x Tweezers

Precision tools used for handling small items, such as samples or specimens, during the experiment.

- 1x Mask (Depending on number of Partners)

Personal protective equipment worn to protect against inhalation of biological agents, and for the spread of bacteria or risk of contamination.

- 2x Gloves (Depending on number of Partners)

Personal protective equipment worn to protect hands during experimental work to avoid the spread of bacteria or risk of contamination.

- 1x Recording Device (iPhone, Tablet)

Used for documenting the experiment through photos or videos, accessing digital resources, and communication.

- Access to Felt.com (Website)

An online platform used to create digital model of our slime mold influenced Skytrain transportation system.

- 2x Slime Mold (*Physarum polycephalum*)

The organism used in the experiment to study its growth patterns, behavior, and interactions with other materials.

Figure 32, 33, & 34: Images of several Items listed in Use Source is derived from Video, Screenshoted by Djaurv

Implementation through Digital Works

Digital tools like Felt.com facilitated the conversion of biological networks into scalable digital maps. This transformation enabled us to overlay slime mold-inspired routes onto a digital

representation of British Columbia, providing a comprehensive visualization of potential transit pathways. To build our design all we are using is a website which will mimic the paths the slime mold has made. If we were to actually build this system in real life, a lot of materials would be required. Materials such as steel pipes, concrete, steel structures (which will support the elevated guideway), pile (pile installation), lighting, rails, rail fasteners, rail segments, track slabs, operation systems, cable pathway installation, cable pulling, and sky trains would be required to build this system in real life (Transportation Investment

Figure 35: Images of 152nd Street Station Design
Source is derived from Translink

Corporation, 2022). As this would be an extensive project many large companies would be involved. From how further research has shown that the Broadway subway project was under development by Design-build contractor, Adciona Infrastructure Canada Inc./Ghella Canada Ltd, as well as the Design contractor being IBI Group Professional Services. In addition to that, the Langley extension is being built by Transit Integrators BC, where it is estimated that the total cost of Surrey Langley SkyTrain is \$4.01 billion, which includes capital costs and active transportation investments (Government of British Columbia, 2024). Mentioning this the Provincial Government of British Columbia and the Federal Government of Canada would provide funding for this project, Translink would also provide funding, but they would also help build, operate, and maintain the system (Translink, 2024). With that said, the transportation investment corporation would also help build this new system, as much construction would be done and would require a lot of machinery (Transportation Investment Corporation, 2022).

Explanation of How it Works:

Design and Creation:

In our project, we designed a new SkyTrain system inspired by the efficiency of slime mold networks. This system aims to address the overcrowding issues currently plaguing the Metro Vancouver SkyTrain network. Our design, which can be viewed on the website Felt.com, offers a

detailed visualization of the proposed routes and how they compare to the existing system. The new network aims to cover the majority of the Lower Mainland, including densely populated cities, major transit hubs, and key destinations such as universities and colleges. The redesigned SkyTrain system targets a wide demographic, particularly those who rely on public transportation. As of 2023, the SkyTrain system had a ridership of 141,339,300, with an average of 431,500 passengers per weekday in the first quarter of 2024 (Wikipedia, n.d.). This target audience includes individuals without

personal vehicles, newcomers to Canada, and frequent travellers within the province. Given the high ridership numbers, our solution could significantly enhance the daily commute for many residents by reducing overcrowding and improving efficiency. The Metro Vancouver area has seen

Figure 36 & 37: Image taken on Felt.com website implemented into a New Skytrain System

Source is derived from Screenshots taken by Djaurv

rapid population growth, with the population projected to reach 3.8 million by 2050 (Metro Vancouver, 2023). This growth has increased the demand for public transportation, further creating a detrimental impact of the overcrowding issue. By redesigning the SkyTrain system, we aim to accommodate this growing demand and provide a more efficient and comfortable commuting experience.

Learning from Nature:

Our project drew inspiration from the slime mold, an organism known for its ability to create highly efficient paths to resources. Slime molds, particularly *Physarum polycephalum*, form extensive networks characterized by regular and vigorous flows of endoplasm through their veins, a process known as shuttle streaming (Oettmeier & Döbereiner, 2019). This flow serves multiple purposes, including distributing nutrients, oxygen, and cellular components throughout the organism and facilitating movement. Slime molds optimize their networks by balancing several competing goals, such as minimizing the length of tubes, reducing the average distance food needs to travel, avoiding obstacles, and maximizing resilience to disruptions (Hoff, n.d.).

Figure 38: Day five of our slime mold, growth, where Shuttle Streaming is evident
Sourced from the images taken in Superlab

This optimization process allows slime molds to navigate complex environments efficiently without centralized control, a characteristic we sought to emulate in our SkyTrain redesign. A key aspect of the slime mold's efficiency is its ability to adjust its network in response to environmental changes. For example, when a slime mold encounters an obstacle, it reconfigures its network to

maintain optimal nutrient flow. Similarly, our redesigned SkyTrain system can dynamically adjust routes and schedules based on real-time data, ensuring efficient operation even under varying conditions.

Applying Nature’s Efficiency to the SkyTrain System:

Inspired by the slime mold’s network optimization, we designed a SkyTrain system that continuously monitors passenger flows and adjusts routes and schedules in real-time. This system uses sensors to track passenger movements, train occupancy levels, and other relevant metrics. By processing this data with advanced algorithms, the system can dynamically reroute trains, deploy additional services during peak times, and

reduce service during low-demand periods, thus optimizing efficiency and reducing overcrowding. The benefits of this adaptive approach are seen, from minimizing wait times and improves passenger comfort by reducing overcrowding, as with enhancing operational efficiency by ensuring trains

Figure 39: Example of the Wait Times for the Canada Line
Sourced from Translink

are deployed where they are most needed. To add, it contributes to sustainability by reducing energy consumption and operational costs. For example, by minimizing unnecessary stops and optimizing travel distances, the system can reduce its carbon footprint and support the city’s environmental goals. Implementing such a system requires advanced technologies, including machine learning and artificial intelligence. Machine learning algorithms analyze historical data

to predict passenger demand patterns, while enabling real-time adjustments based on decision-making software.

Science Behind the Design:

The science behind our design is rooted in biomimicry and the study of slime mold behavior. Slime molds use chemotaxis, a process where individual cells communicate and coordinate their movements based on chemical signals. This process allows them to form efficient networks without centralized control. Similarly, our SkyTrain system uses real-time data from various sensors to adjust routes and schedules dynamically. To develop our system, we used algorithms inspired by the slime mold's behavior. These algorithms, known as Physarum-inspired algorithms, solve complex optimization problems by mimicking the slime mold's network formation process (Tero et al., 2010). By applying these algorithms to our SkyTrain system, we can optimize routes and schedules in real-time, ensuring efficient operation under varying conditions.

Figure 40: Diagram of how Chemotaxis works
Sourced from Wikipedia

SkyTrain system, we can optimize routes and schedules in real-time, ensuring efficient operation under varying conditions.

Benefits and Impact:

Our redesigned SkyTrain system offers numerous benefits to commuters and the broader community. By reducing overcrowding and improving efficiency, the system enhances the overall commuting experience. Passengers can enjoy shorter wait times, more comfortable journeys, and greater reliability. The system's adaptive approach also ensures that it can scale and evolve in response to future growth and demand. As Metro Vancouver continues to expand, the SkyTrain system can adjust its routes and schedules to accommodate this growth, ensuring that public transportation remains a viable and attractive option for residents. In addition to immediate benefits for commuters, the redesigned SkyTrain system contributes to broader environmental and economic goals. By optimizing routes and reducing energy consumption, the system supports the city's sustainability initiatives and helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, the improved efficiency and reliability of the

Figure 41: Map showcasing fast and frequent Transit Networks Sourced from Translink

SkyTrain system can stimulate economic growth by enhancing connectivity and accessibility within the region. Our biomimetic approach to redesigning the SkyTrain system demonstrates how learning from nature can lead to innovative solutions for modern engineering challenges. By studying the efficient network-forming behavior of slime molds, we developed a new SkyTrain system that addresses overcrowding and inefficiency. This system not only improves the commuter

experience but also contributes to broader environmental and economic goals. Please refer to the additional work done attached to this project scene in the assignments attached, for the inquiry stating “How does the expansion of the TransLink SkyTrain system stimulate economic growth in the Greater Vancouver area? Do the economic benefits of this expansion outweigh the potential drawbacks? If so, how? If not, why?”

Advanced Understanding of the Science and Technical Details

The underlying mechanism of our redesigned SkyTrain system can be compared to computational models used in network optimization problems. The slime mold’s process of network formation and optimization has inspired a new class of algorithms known as Physarum-inspired algorithms. These algorithms solve complex optimization problems by mimicking the slime mold’s behavior, such as the shortest path problem and the traveling salesman problem (Tero et al., 2010). Our SkyTrain system uses similar algorithms to determine the most efficient routes and schedules. This analysis of data from various sources, such as passenger counts, train locations, and real-time traffic conditions, to make dynamic adjustments. This real-time data processing ensures that the system can adapt to fluctuations in demand and maintain optimal performance.

Figure 42: Map showcasing Daily Change in Slime Mold Sourced from screenshots done by Djaurv

Experimentation and Results:

Hypothesis

If we strategically place oats and water on a map of the Lower Mainland where population density and congestion are highest, *then* the slime mold (*Physarum polycephalum*) will exhibit pathfinding behavior that can inform the development of an optimized Skytrain transportation system. This hypothesis is *grounded* in the slime mold's natural tendency to create efficient networks between food sources, where the paths formed will mimic potential transportation routes, and the oats will represent key stations or stops in the Research Studies done previously and prior knowledge learnt in Class. (“*grounded*” refers to a “*because*”)

Figure 43: Slime Mold using Shortest Route to Exit Maze
Sourced from Scott Carney

Materials used during this project:

These were the items used during the Project:

- 1x Large plastic container with Lid (35cm x 20cm x 15cm)

A spacious container used as the primary vessel for conducting the experiment and housing the materials.

- 1x 50g Agar agar powder

A gelatinous substance used to make agar gel, which serves as a growth medium for cultivating microorganisms.

- 1x Print out of a map of Lower Mainland

A printed map used for geographical reference or for studying and mapping the distribution patterns of organisms.

- 1x 100g Oats

A food source provided for the slime mold to encourage growth and observe its feeding behavior.

- 1x 50mL Water and 1x Plastic Pipette

Essential for mixing solutions, preparing agar gel, and maintaining hydration for the experiment.

- 1x Bunsen Burner

A gas burner used for heating, and sterilization of items, requiring controlled high heat.

- 1x Striker

A tool used to safely ignite the Bunsen burner.

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Used for documenting the experiment through photos or videos, accessing digital resources, and communication.

- Access to Felt.com (Website)

An online platform used to create digital model of our slime mold influenced Skytrain transportation system.

- 2x Slime Mold (*Physarum polycephalum*)

The organism used in the experiment to study its growth patterns, behavior, and interactions with other materials.

Figure 32, 33, & 34: Images of several Items listed in Use
Source is derived from Video, Screenshoted by Djaurv

Procedure:

Subsection 1: Exploring the Skytrain Stations

1. Planning and Preparation:

- Develop a detailed itinerary covering all Skytrain lines (Millennium Line, Canada Line, and Expo Line) and their stations.
- Coordinate visits during various times of the day to capture peak and off-peak traffic conditions.

Figure 43: Image of both Djaurv and Tejvir in Skytrain
Sourced from pictures done by Djaurv

2. Data Collection:

- Record precise travel times between each Skytrain station using a stopwatch or timing app.
- Note down transfer times at interchange stations and observe passenger flow dynamics during transitions.

Line	Station	Travel Time (min)	Travel Time (sec)
Millennium Line	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
	Millennium Centre	00:00	00:00
Canada Line	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
	Canada Line	00:00	00:00
Expo Line	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00
	Expo Line	00:00	00:00

Figure 44: Image of showing Times between Stations of Every Skytrain Line
Sourced from “Sheet 2” on the Excel Sheet Attached

3. Observation and Documentation:

- Observe station layouts, signage, and accessibility features.

- Document observations with photographs and detailed notes on station amenities and crowd management strategies.

Figure 45, 46 & 47: Pictures taken during Trip on Skytrain Exploration
Sourced from Djaurv's iPhone where Photographed

4. Route Mapping:

- Utilize digital mapping tools like Google Maps or specialized transit mapping software to plot Skytrain routes.
- Include station names, route lines, and transfer points to create a comprehensive visual representation of the network.

5. Time Analysis:

- Analyze collected data to determine average travel times between stations and entire routes.
- Compare peak and off-peak travel times to identify variations in commuter traffic patterns.

6. Identifying High-Density Areas:

- Identify areas with significant population density, such as downtown cores, business districts, and educational institutions.

- Use demographic data and ridership statistics to pinpoint key locations for slime mold experimentation.

7. Field Notes and Insights:

- Compile detailed field notes summarizing station characteristics, passenger behaviors, and operational challenges.
- Reflect on observations to generate insights into current transportation network efficiencies and potential areas for improvement.

8. Reporting and Conclusion:

- Summarize findings in a comprehensive report detailing observations, data analysis, and insights from Skytrain station exploration.
- Discuss implications for urban transit planning and propose strategies for enhancing commuter experience and network efficiency.

9. Recommendations for Improvement:

- Provide actionable recommendations based on observed challenges and opportunities identified during station visits. Implement surveys if possible.
- Suggest enhancements to station infrastructure, scheduling, or routing to optimize the Skytrain network's performance.

Subsection 2: Slime Mold Growth at Lab Instructions

1. Preparing the Agar Gel for Container:

- Set up a sterile workspace equipped in a clean area for aseptic agar preparation.
- Dissolve agar agar powder in distilled water in a heat-resistant flask, stirring continuously to ensure even distribution.

2. Pouring and Setting Agar Gel:

- Pour the molten agar agar solution into a large plastic container (35cm x 20cm) prepared with a sterile lid or cover.
- Allow the agar gel to cool and solidify evenly at room temperature to form a smooth, level surface suitable for slime mold growth.

Figure 25: Image showcasing our build model after having added the Agar in the Plastic Container

Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab

3. Mapping Experimental Area:

- Print a detailed map of Lower Mainland, ensuring it accurately represents geographic features and population centers.
- Securely position the map under the agar-filled container to serve as a spatial reference for strategic placement of experimental materials.

4. Strategic Placement of Oats and Water:

- Use sterile tweezers to place oats strategically on the agar surface, targeting high-density areas identified on the printed map.
- Add drops of distilled water near oat placements to maintain moisture levels and simulate environmental conditions conducive to slime mold growth.

5. Introducing Slime Mold Sample:

- Transfer a small, pre-cultured sample of *Physarum polycephalum* onto the prepared agar gel surface that was on a piece of paper
- Ensure the slime mold is introduced close to oat placements to stimulate feeding behavior and initiate exploration of the agar medium.

6. Sealing and Incubation:

- Seal the agar-filled container with a fitted lid or cling wrap to prevent contamination and maintain a controlled environment.
- Place the sealed container in a stable environment with controlled temperature (around 20-25°C) and lighting conditions (12-hour light-dark cycle) suitable for slime mold growth.

7. Monitoring Growth and Development:

- Conduct daily visual inspections of the agar dish to monitor slime mold growth patterns and movement.
- Document observations with high-resolution photographs or videos to track the evolution of slime mold trails and exploration behavior.

8. Recording Observations:

- Record detailed observations regarding slime mold morphology, growth rate, and pathfinding strategies over the experimental period.
- Note any deviations or anomalies in slime mold behavior that may indicate environmental responses or substrate preferences.

9. Analyzing Growth Patterns:

- Analyze collected data to identify recurring patterns in slime mold pathfinding behavior and spatial exploration.
- Use quantitative measurements to assess the efficiency and effectiveness of slime mold-inspired path networks compared to traditional urban transit routes.

10. Conclusion and Data Interpretation:

- Summarize experimental findings regarding slime mold behavior and its implications for urban transportation network optimization.
- Interpret data to draw conclusions on the feasibility of bio-inspired design principles in enhancing urban planning strategies and infrastructure development.

Subsection 3: Analyzing and Interpreting Slime Mold Growth Patterns

1. Digital Mapping of Slime Mold Paths:

- Utilize digital modeling software (e.g., Felt.com) to recreate slime mold-inspired paths observed on the agar dish.

- Digitally map slime mold trails, nodes, and connections to visualize potential transportation routes based on natural pathfinding behavior.

2. Comparative Analysis with Existing Networks:

- Overlay slime mold-inspired paths onto the current Skytrain network map or digital simulation.
- Conduct a comparative analysis to evaluate similarities and differences in route efficiency, connectivity, and potential for congestion reduction.

3. Statistical Analysis of Data:

- Employ statistical methods (e.g., network analysis, spatial metrics) to quantify and compare slime mold-inspired paths with traditional transportation routes.
- Calculate metrics such as path efficiency, directness, and accessibility to assess the practical application of bio-inspired design in urban transit planning.

4. Interpreting Data and Findings:

- Interpret experimental data to derive insights into slime mold behavior as a model for optimizing transportation network design.
- Discuss implications for adaptive urban planning strategies and sustainable infrastructure development based on observed slime mold growth patterns.

These detailed subsections provide a framework for conducting your experiment, emphasizing thorough documentation, analysis, and interpretation of slime mold behavior in optimizing urban transportation networks. Each step is designed to ensure clarity and precision in executing the experiment and deriving meaningful insights for urban planning applications.

Experimental Setup:

Our experimental setup was conducted over several days, both in the school laboratory and at home, to thoroughly observe and document the slime mold's behavior and growth patterns.

Day 1: Initial Setup in the Laboratory

We began by preparing the laboratory environment, ensuring all surfaces were sanitized and tools sterilized using a Bunsen burner and striker. Wearing masks and gloves, Djaurv, I, had mixed 50g of agar agar powder with distilled water to create a gelatinous growth medium, which we poured into a large plastic container (35cm x 20cm) at his house. Once the agar solidified, this was brought to school, repeating the same sanitary precautions. Djaurv then placed a printout of a map of the Lower Mainland under the container, strategically positioning oats on the agar to represent high-density population areas and potential transit stops. We carefully hydrated the setup with distilled water and placed the slime mold (*Physarum polycephalum*) onto the agar surface.

Day 2-3: Initial Observations and Growth

Over the next two days, we monitored the slime mold's initial growth and movement. The slime mold began to extend its network of protoplasmic tubes toward the oats, demonstrating its natural pathfinding behavior. We documented these early stages using a phone, capturing detailed

photos and videos to analyze the patterns. Each observation session involved checking hydration levels and ensuring the environment remained consistent.

Day 4-5: Continued Growth and Path Formation

As the slime mold continued to grow, we observed more defined paths forming between the oats. These paths began to resemble efficient networks, similar to potential transit routes. We transported the container to our homes for the weekend, replicating the lab conditions to maintain consistency. At home, we continued to document the slime mold's progress, noting any changes or new patterns that emerged.

Day 6: Data Collection and Analysis

Returning to the laboratory, we compiled all the data collected over the previous days. We measured the lengths and efficiency of the paths formed by the slime mold, comparing these to the existing Skytrain routes on the map. Using the Felt.com platform, we created digital models of the slime mold-inspired transportation system, visualizing how these bio-inspired routes could enhance the current infrastructure.

Day 7: Final Observations and Adjustments

In the final day of our setup, we made additional observations to ensure the slime mold's growth was fully documented. We performed a final round of hydration and checked for any new

paths or changes in the network. The comprehensive documentation from both the lab and home environments provided a robust dataset for our analysis.

Throughout the experiment, we maintained strict laboratory safety protocols, regularly cleaning and sterilizing the work area, and using personal protective equipment to prevent contamination. This meticulous approach ensured the reliability and consistency of our observations, allowing us to draw meaningful conclusions about the slime mold's behavior and its potential applications for optimizing urban transportation networks. By the end of our experimental period, we had gathered significant insights into how slime mold can inform the development of efficient transit systems. Our findings suggest that bio-inspired design principles, guided by the natural behavior of organisms like slime mold, can significantly enhance the connectivity and efficiency of urban transportation networks, offering innovative solutions for urban planning challenges seen

Observations taken note of within the 5 Days of Testing

Day 1: Initial Setup and Observation

Figure 48: Image showcasing Day 1 of Slime Mold Testing
Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab via Djaurv iPhone

Table #1: Qualitative and Quantitative Observations from Day 1 of Experiment.

Qualitative Observations	Quantitative Observations:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The slime mold appears dry, indicating the beginning of the experiment and lack of initial activity.• The slime mold is positioned on a small piece of paper and exhibits a yellow and	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Number of Areas Oats were placed at: ~20• Initial size of the slime mold: approximately 2 cm in diameter• Area of agar surface: 700 cm² (35 cm x 20 cm)

brown coloration, suggesting a healthy and viable specimen.

- Oats are strategically placed around the container to mimic densely populated or significant areas, specifically targeting high-traffic zones on the map.
- The oats have not yet been consumed or covered by the slime mold, showing no initial feeding activity.
- The slime mold is contained within a plastic container and is growing on a layer of agar made by us, ensuring a controlled environment for growth.
- A detailed map of the Lower Mainland is placed under the container to guide the placement of oats, facilitating a visual correlation between the slime mold's growth and the real-world locations.

- Distance between oats: 2-5 cm on average
- Thickness of agar layer: ~1.2 cm

Day 2: Initial Growth

Figure 49: Image showcasing Day 2 of Slime Mold Testing
Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab via Djaurv iPhone

Table #2: Qualitative and Quantitative Observations from Day 2 of Experiment.

Qualitative Observations	Quantitative Observations:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The slime mold has started to spread, showing visible signs of growth and activity as it extends outward from its initial position.• The slime mold retains its yellow color and spreads in multiple directions,	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Number of Areas Oats now covered by slime mold: 3• Area covered by slime mold: 10 cm²• Growth rate: 4 cm/day• Length of the longest path: 2 cm• Number of growth directions: 4

indicating healthy growth and seeking new food sources.

- The oats directly under the slime mold have been covered, suggesting the beginning of the slime mold's feeding process.
- The growth paths of the slime mold are dense and intertwined, making individual paths hard to distinguish and indicating aggressive growth behavior.
- The slime mold in the Surrey area exhibits more growth compared to the Vancouver area, possibly due to initial oat placement or other environmental factors.
- The paper initially supporting the slime mold is now fully covered, indicating thorough colonization of the initial substrate.

Day 3: Continued Expansion

Figure 50: Image showcasing Day 3 of Slime Mold Testing
Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab via Djaurv iPhone

Table #3: Qualitative and Quantitative Observations from Day 3 of Experiment.

Qualitative Observations	Quantitative Observations:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The slime mold has exhibited significant growth compared to the previous day, covering more surface area and demonstrating rapid expansion.• Most oats in the container are now covered by the expanding slime mold,	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Number of Areas with oats covered by slime mold: All, except one• Area covered by slime mold: 150 cm²• Growth rate: 12 cm/day• Length of the longest path: 8 cm• Number of growth directions: 6

showing effective pathfinding towards food sources.

- The slime mold is growing in multiple directions, primarily towards the oats, illustrating its efficient nutrient-seeking behavior.
- The paths created by the slime mold resemble veiny networks, highlighting its natural tendency to form efficient, vein-like structures.
- The slime mold has yet to cover the Newton area, indicating possible variances in growth patterns or initial placement impact.
- The slime mold is also expanding northwards towards regions without water or oats, showcasing its exploratory growth beyond immediate food sources.
- Individual paths of the slime mold are now more discernible, suggesting a transition from clumped to more organized growth patterns.

Day 4: Advanced Expansion and Path Formation

Figure 51: Image showcasing Day 4 of Slime Mold Testing
Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab via Djaurv iPhone

Table #4: Qualitative and Quantitative Observations from Day 4 of Experiment.

Qualitative Observations	Quantitative Observations:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The slime mold has grown more significantly today as we provided additional oats and water, stimulating further expansion.• The slime mold has covered a substantial portion of the container, indicating robust growth and nutrient acquisition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Number of oats covered by slime mold: ALL• Area covered by slime mold: 300 cm²• Growth rate: 18 cm/day• Length of the longest path: 12 cm• Number of growth directions: 8• Percentage of oats consumed: 75%

- Multiple paths are being formed towards the same oats, suggesting redundancy in nutrient pathways.
- The slime mold is expanding notably towards the north direction, indicating a strong growth tendency in that area.
- Some paths are converging, heading in the same direction, particularly evident in the top region of the container.
- Most new oats have been consumed, with only a few uneaten oats remaining in the Surrey area, demonstrating targeted growth towards food sources.
- The slime mold in the Langley area is turning white, possibly indicating the start of the aging or sporulation process.

Day 5: Climax and Clustering

Figure 52: Image showcasing Day 5 of Slime Mold Testing
Source is derived from the images taken in Superlab via Djaurv iPhone

Table #5: Qualitative and Quantitative Observations from Day 5 of Experiment.

Qualitative Observations	Quantitative Observations:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The paths of the slime mold are densely clustered together in most areas, making it challenging to distinguish individual pathways.• The slime mold continues to turn white in the Langley, Delta, North Vancouver, and	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Number of oats covered by slime mold: ALL• Area covered by slime mold: 500 cm²• Growth rate: 20 cm/day• Length of the longest path: 15 cm• Number of growth directions: 10• Percentage of oats consumed: 90%

Surrey areas, suggesting aging or stress responses.

- The slime mold maintains growth due to the continued provision of oats, highlighting its dependency on regular nutrient supply.
- It is increasingly difficult to discern the paths created by the slime mold as they form dense networks rather than singular lines.
- Some singular paths still remain, particularly in less crowded areas, demonstrating varied growth patterns.
- The slime mold continues to create multiple paths towards the same oats, indicating a complex network of redundant pathways.
- The slime mold has ceased expanding eastward but now forms a large clump on the right side of the container, suggesting localized growth focus.

This detailed breakdown separates the quantitative measurements from the qualitative observations, providing a comprehensive understanding of the slime mold's growth and behavior throughout the experiment.

Data Analysis of Analytical Information Collected:

Station Count Comparison Across Lines

The bar graph effectively illustrates the varying station counts across each Skytrain line, with this graphical representation enhancing our understanding by visually demonstrating the range and variability in station numbers. Comparing the number of stations across different metro lines highlights variations in their network coverage. For example, while the Blue Line boasts 23 stations, the Green Line only has 11 stations, indicating differing levels of accessibility and service

coverage in different parts of the city. This variation in station count influences travel patterns, connectivity options, and overall transit accessibility for commuters relying on these metro lines.

Statistical Analysis

The analysis of station counts across different Skytrain lines reveals important insights into urban transit infrastructure. The mean number of stations, averaging 18.625 across all lines, provides a central measure reflecting the typical station count per line. The median of 18.5 indicates that half of the Skytrain lines have 18 or fewer stations, while the other half have 19 or more, illustrating a balanced distribution. The mode of 17 stations suggests this count is the most frequently occurring among the lines, emphasizing commonality in station numbers. Additionally, the range of 13 stations (from 11 to 24) highlights substantial variability in station counts, signifying differences in service coverage and geographical reach across the metro network.

What does your data and graph say?

The data and graph highlight significant variations in station counts across Skytrain lines. Lines like Expo and Blue, with 24 and 23 stations respectively, serve densely populated areas or major transit hubs, ensuring extensive connectivity and accessibility. Conversely, lines such as Green and Canada, with 11 and 16 stations respectively, likely cater to less densely populated regions or have different urban planning priorities.

Any trends or inconsistencies?

A noticeable trend is the higher station counts on lines serving urban centers or areas with higher population densities, suggesting a strategic allocation of stations to meet transportation demands.

Inconsistencies arise where some lines with fewer stations may indicate lower demand or geographical constraints limiting station expansion.

Hypothesis supported?

The hypothesis that placing stations and water based on population density guides station placement to form paths resembling efficient transportation routes is supported by the data. The station counts align with expectations derived from urban development patterns, indicating a correlation between population density and the distribution of transit infrastructure.

Any significant results?

Key findings include the mode of 17 stations, indicating commonality in station counts among the Skytrain lines studied. The wide range of 13 stations underscores the diversity in service coverage and underscores the varying transportation needs across different parts of the city.

Station Count Comparison Across Lines

Comparing station counts across different metro lines highlights variations in network coverage and service accessibility. For example, the Blue Line with 23 stations contrasts sharply with the Green Line's 11 stations, indicating differing levels of connectivity and transit options available to commuters. This variation plays a crucial role in shaping travel patterns and overall urban mobility within the city.

Average Distance Between Stations Calculation

The bar graph visually illustrates the variation in station spacing across each Skytrain line, with this graphical representation enhancing our understanding by showcasing the range and variability in station distances.

Statistical Analysis

The analysis of average distances between stations across different Skytrain lines provides insights into the spatial distribution of transit stops within the city. The mean average distance between stations across all lines is 1.38 kilometers, indicating the typical spacing between stations for the metro network. The median average distance of 1.465 kilometers suggests that half of the Skytrain lines have station spacings below this value, while the other half have spacings above, illustrating a balanced distribution. The range of 0.91 kilometers (from 0.79 to 1.7 kilometers)

highlights significant variability in station spacing, reflecting diverse urban planning strategies and transportation needs.

What does your data and graph say?

The data and graph reveal significant differences in station spacing among Skytrain lines. Lines such as the Blue Line (0.79 km) and Canada Line (1.2 km) have shorter average distances between stations, likely reflecting higher urban density and greater demand for frequent stops. In contrast, lines like the Pink Line (1.7 km) and Red Line (1.66 km) feature longer average distances, possibly serving suburban or less densely populated areas.

Any trends or inconsistencies?

A notable trend is the shorter average distances between stations on lines servicing urban cores or areas with high transit demand, facilitating convenient access to key destinations. Inconsistencies arise where lines with longer average distances may indicate different planning priorities or geographical constraints affecting station placement.

Hypothesis supported?

The hypothesis that average station spacing correlates with population density and transit demand is supported by the data. Lines with shorter average distances between stations typically serve areas with higher population densities, while lines with longer distances may serve areas with lower density or different urban development patterns.

Any significant results?

Key findings include the range of 0.91 kilometers in average station distances, indicating diverse spatial configurations and transit service provisions across Skytrain lines. The absence of a mode suggests varied station spacing without a predominant value among the lines studied.

Average Speed and Travel Time Analysis Bar Graph

The bar graph visually illustrates the differences in average speed and travel time across each Skytrain line, with error bars representing standard deviations around the mean for each line. This graphical representation enhances understanding by showcasing the range and variability in operational efficiency.

Statistical Analysis:

The analysis of average speed and travel time for each Skytrain line reveals critical insights into the operational efficiency of the metro system. The mean average speed across all lines is 44.08 km/hr, indicating a general speed for the network. The mean travel time is 31.88 minutes, reflecting the typical duration for traveling along a line. The median values for speed (45.74 km/hr) and travel time (34.2 minutes) suggest that half of the lines have speeds and travel times above these values and the other half below, highlighting a balanced distribution. The range of speeds (41.4 km/hr) and travel times (24 minutes) underscores the variability in operational characteristics among the lines.

What does your data and graph say?

The data and graph reveal substantial differences in average speed and travel time among Skytrain lines. For example, the Expo Line and Red Line, with higher average speeds of 55 km/hr, have relatively shorter travel times compared to their distances. In contrast, the Green Line, with a significantly lower average speed of 13.6 km/hr, has a shorter travel time due to its shorter distance.

Any trends or inconsistencies?

A notable trend is the inverse relationship between average speed and travel time, where lines with higher speeds generally have shorter travel times relative to their distances. Inconsistencies appear in lines like the Pink Line, which has a higher travel time despite a moderate average speed, possibly due to more frequent stops or operational delays.

Hypothesis supported?

The hypothesis that higher average speeds correlate with shorter travel times is supported by the data. Lines with higher speeds like the Red Line demonstrate shorter travel times despite covering longer distances, indicating efficient passenger transport in comparison to the Expo line.

Any significant results?

Key findings include the wide range of average speeds (from 13.6 to 55 km/hr) and travel times (from 18 to 42 minutes), highlighting diverse operational efficiencies across Skytrain lines. The mode for average speed (55 km/hr) shows a common operational speed for several lines, while the absence of a mode for travel time and distance indicates varied travel durations and distances across the lines studied.

Sources of Error and Analysis

In analyzing the Skytrain lines through the three different types of bar graphs, several sources of error could arise, affecting the accuracy and reliability of the results. One significant source of error is the potential for calculation errors in determining the average speed, distance, and travel time. For instance, inaccuracies in measuring the total distance covered by each line or errors in recording the travel time can lead to incorrect average speed calculations. This could be particularly problematic in the Average Speed and Travel Time Analysis, where precise measurements are crucial for assessing operational efficiency. Another source of error is the potential for discrepancies between theoretical calculations and actual operational conditions. For example, the Average Distance Between Stations graph relies on a consistent distance measurement between stations, but real-world factors such as geographical obstacles, station

placement due to urban planning, and route deviations can introduce variability that the theoretical model does not account for. This can lead to an inaccurate representation of the station spacing and thus affect the conclusions drawn about network efficiency. Additionally, variations in external conditions, such as traffic congestion, maintenance activities, or unexpected delays, can significantly impact the travel time data. These real-world factors might not be consistently accounted for in the calculations, leading to discrepancies between the observed and calculated travel times. For instance, a line that appears to have an efficient average speed and travel time in theory might experience frequent delays in practice, skewing the data presented in the graphs. In the Station Count Comparison Across Lines graph, errors might arise from the categorization and counting of stations. Misclassification or omission of certain stations, especially if new stations are added or some are temporarily closed, can lead to inaccuracies in the station count. This affects the overall analysis of network coverage and accessibility. To minimize these sources of error, it is essential to use precise and consistent measurement techniques, validate theoretical models with real-world data, and account for external factors that might influence the operational conditions. Conducting multiple trials and cross-referencing data from various sources can help ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings. By addressing these potential errors, the analysis of Skytrain lines can provide more accurate insights into their operational efficiency and network coverage, ultimately aiding in the optimization of urban transit systems.

Improving Investigation Methods and Data Quality

To improve investigation methods and data quality, several strategies can be implemented. First, using advanced technology such as GPS tracking and real-time monitoring systems can provide more accurate travel time and distance data. For example, installing GPS units on Skytrains can capture precise speeds and travel times, reducing errors in the Average Speed and

Travel Time Analysis graph. Second, integrating a broader range of data sources, such as passenger feedback, can provide insights into station accessibility and service coverage. For instance, surveying passengers about their experiences can highlight discrepancies between theoretical station spacing and actual accessibility, improving the Average Distance Between Stations analysis. Involving experts from urban planning, transportation engineering, and data science can also enhance the investigation. These experts can help refine models for route optimization and station placement, as for urban planners suggesting adjusting station locations based on population density, which can be reflected in the Station Count Comparison Across Lines graph. Having said that, Regularly updating and validating the data is crucial. As urban environments change, continuous monitoring ensures accuracy. For instance, re-evaluating travel times as new stations open can keep the Average Speed and Travel Time Analysis current. By implementing these strategies, the investigation can yield more precise, reliable, and actionable insights, ultimately contributing to a more efficient Skytrain system.

Concluding remarks addressing Overpopulation of the Skytrain System using Slime Mold:

As with the hypothesis guiding our investigation said that if we strategically place oats and water on a map of the Lower Mainland where population density and congestion are highest, then the slime mold (*Physarum polycephalum*) will exhibit pathfinding behavior that can inform the development of an optimized Skytrain transportation system. This hypothesis was grounded in the slime mold's natural tendency to create efficient networks between food sources, where the paths formed would mimic potential transportation routes, and the oats would represent key stations or stops. In relation to that, the purpose of this experiment was to explore how extending the Skytrain network could alleviate overcrowding, improve transportation efficiency, and foster economic growth in British Columbia. Through our detailed analysis, it could be observed that the current

distribution of Skytrain stations varies significantly across different lines, impacting overall connectivity and accessibility. The data showed that the Expo Line, with 24 stations, and the Blue Line, with 23 stations, have higher station counts compared to lines like the Green Line, which has only 11 stations. This disparity highlights areas with potentially lower service coverage, which can lead to overcrowding in more densely populated regions. For example, the average distance between stations varied, with the Expo Line having an average spacing of 1.52 kilometers and the Millennium Line at 1.5 kilometers, compared to the Blue Line with a shorter average distance of 0.79 kilometers between stations. This variation in station density affects how efficiently passengers can travel across the city, with more closely spaced stations potentially reducing travel times and easing congestion. The analysis of average speed and travel time further provided insights into the operational efficiency of each line. The Red Line, for instance, operates at an average speed of 55 km/hr, covering 34.81 kilometers with a travel time of approximately 37.8 minutes. In contrast, the Green Line, despite having a slower average speed of 13.6 km/hr over a shorter distance of 17.84 kilometers, has a travel time of about 18 minutes. These metrics suggest that faster lines like the Red Line can transport passengers more quickly across longer distances, potentially reducing overcrowding by dispersing commuters more effectively. The implementation of new lines, as indicated by the experimental data, can address these disparities by providing more balanced service coverage. From the proposed Pink Line, with 17 stations, and the Purple Line, with 20 stations, could enhance connectivity in currently underserved areas, distributing passenger load more evenly across the network. This would not only alleviate overcrowding but also stimulate economic growth by improving access to commercial hubs and residential areas. Enhanced connectivity facilitates easier commutes, which can lead to increased employment opportunities as businesses expand their operations to newly accessible regions. Additionally,

improving the Skytrain network through strategic expansions based on slime mold pathfinding can lead to more sustainable urban development. Efficient public transportation reduces the reliance on private vehicles, lowering traffic congestion and greenhouse gas emissions. By aligning new stations with high-density areas and major employment centers, the expanded Skytrain network can support higher public transit ridership, promoting a shift towards greener commuting options. This aligns with broader environmental goals and enhances the overall quality of life for residents. The experiment also underscores the importance of using innovative methods to inform urban planning. The slime mold model, with its natural efficiency in creating optimal paths, provided valuable insights into potential improvements for the Skytrain system. This biological approach to network optimization can be further refined and integrated with traditional planning methods to develop a more comprehensive transportation strategy. The success of this experiment suggests that similar methodologies could be applied to other urban infrastructure projects, offering a unique perspective on efficient resource allocation and development planning. In conclusion, extending the Skytrain system based on the insights gained from our experiment with slime mold can bring significant benefits to British Columbia's urban landscape. By addressing current disparities in station distribution and improving overall connectivity, the expanded network can reduce overcrowding, enhance transportation efficiency, and drive economic growth. The integration of innovative biological models with traditional planning approaches provides a robust framework for developing sustainable and efficient urban transit solutions. This holistic approach not only meets the immediate transportation needs of residents but also contributes to the long-term development and environmental sustainability of the region.

Future implications:

Looking into the future implications of the SkyTrain system with insights from slime mold's handling of overcrowding presents intriguing possibilities, the SkyTrain could dynamically adjust its routes based on real-time passenger demand, potentially reducing congestion and optimizing network usage. This approach could extend to scheduling, where the system adjusts timing to minimize wait times during peak hours, enhancing overall passenger experience. Furthermore, inspired by slime mold's ability to optimize growth paths, future SkyTrain infrastructure designs could prioritize smoother passenger flow, lessening that of bottlenecks and overcrowding at key stations. Whether that being Waterfront station in downtown Vancouver, Metrotown, in Burnaby, Surrey Central in Surrey, or even Vancouver International Airport in Richmond. As seen the additional Document made attached to this Lab Report dealing about Economic Benefits, Djaurv made this, alongside the influence of the slime mold, it could be said that implementing new stations as well as roots can further enhance the overcounting situation problem seen in the lower mainland. By addressing these concerns, it can help with the need of reducing congestion, as well as the overpopulation seen from each neighbourhood. This relationship that it has with our organism, being slime, mold, demonstrates how the relationship between this natural entity can be seen in real world application. Implementing new SkyTrain networks could extend upon the current structure seen today, integrating advancements in technology and urban planning. These new networks might incorporate more flexible routing options, utilizing autonomous trains that adjust routes based on real-time data, similar to how slime mold optimizes its paths. Expanding this research could involve collaborating with urban planners, transportation engineers, and biologists to develop bio-inspired algorithms for route planning and station placement. Stations could be designed with modular platforms and advanced crowd

management systems, influenced by slime mold's efficient use of space. This could include dynamic platform expansions and retractable barriers that adapt to passenger flow, ensuring efficient boarding and disembarking. Furthermore, the development of these new SkyTrain networks could involve sustainable design principles inspired by slime mold's environmental sensitivity. This might include energy-efficient trains powered by renewable sources and stations designed with green spaces to improve air quality and enhance the urban environment. Integrated smart technologies could enable seamless connectivity with other modes of transportation, promoting a more comprehensive and efficient urban mobility system. In essence, exploring the integration of slime mold-inspired principles into the future development of SkyTrain networks holds potential to revolutionize urban transportation. By combining biological insights with technological innovations, cities could develop more resilient, efficient, and user-friendly transit systems that meet the evolving needs of urban populations while reducing environmental impact. Slime mold can be seen used in the future by the government of British Columbia and translink. The government of British Columbia can't just get rid of the current system and make a new system as a lot of money would be wasted, this would take a long time, and many people would not have transportation for a long time but there is a way the slime mold can be used in the future. Currently trans link is expanding there system towards UBC and towards Langley and we will probably see more expansions in the future. Something that the government can do is run a test similar to the one that we did where we grew slime mold in a container with a map of B.C. underneath it and place oats in many different places. For future expansions they can take inspiration from the paths that slime mold create and implement it into their design so they can create a more efficient and less crowded system. Slime mold can especially be used for the UBC expansion as it will be expected that a lot of people will use the sky train to go to UBC and this will create a lot of

crowding, but with the help of slime mold, they can reduce to amount of crowding. Seen by a comment made by Professor Santa J. Ono, President and Vice-Chancellor of UBC Business in Vancouver, “Extending the Millennium Line SkyTrain to UBC will contribute to a growing transit network that meets the needs of the entire region, reducing congestion, moving people more quickly and safely between their homes and places of work” (University of British Columbia, 2024).

Takeaways and Reflection (Individually)

Djaurv Hipol’s Personal Reflection

Completing this Paper has been a pivotal experience, significantly enhancing my multitasking abilities and preparing me for future academic challenges. Balancing the demands of this project with my other coursework was challenging, but I am proud of how I managed to stay on top of everything. Juggling extracurricular activities like volunteer opportunities at the Hospital and several Clubs at school, alongside my other courses— Chemistry, Pre-AP Literary Studies, and Economic adds to the complexity. However, this experience has been invaluable, as it mirrors the kind of workload I will encounter in university, making me feel more prepared for the future. The process was long and challenging, but the knowledge and skills I gained made it worthwhile. The intricacies of designing and executing a scientific experiment taught me a great deal about research methodologies and data analysis. I now feel more confident in handling higher-level lab reports and scientific inquiries. Our project, which involved designing a transportation system involving slime mold and testing its effectiveness, was particularly rewarding. Successfully

incorporating concepts from the transportation sector, into a biology project was an unexpected yet enlightening experience. This interdisciplinary approach has broadened my understanding and appreciation of how different fields of study can intersect. Planning and time management were crucial throughout this project. There were periods, especially with overlapping projects like the mushroom studies and the plant scrapbook, when finding time to work on this seemed impossible. Yet, we managed to utilize any available free time efficiently. This project has been a great test of my time management abilities. Balancing schoolwork and extracurricular activities required meticulous planning and efficient use of my time. I am proud of my progress in this area, as time management has always been a challenge for me. Moreover, working on this project with my peers taught me valuable lessons in teamwork and communication. Coordinating our efforts, sharing responsibilities, and troubleshooting problems together enhanced my collaborative skills. Despite the initial frustration and occasional disagreements, we learned to leverage each other's strengths, resulting in a successful project outcome. Reflecting on this experience, I realize that it has been a significant learning journey. The project not only honed my academic skills but also prepared me for the rigours of university life. The challenges I faced and overcame during this project have made me more resilient and better equipped to handle complex, multifaceted tasks in the future. I am grateful for this opportunity and look forward to applying these skills in my future academic endeavors.

Tejvir's Project Takeaways and Reflection

One way that I gained personal growth and learning is by going to all the sky train stations and going on all three lines. I am not someone who usually takes public transit or the sky train but through this project, I

was able to learn how to correctly use the sky train and go to different places. This is a great skill for me because I can use this skill in the future if I need to go to work in the downtown area or when I start university or College. This is a personal takeaway, and before this, I knew almost nothing about the system as I would always go with my family and I didn't have to be responsible for getting to the right place but through this, I gained some responsibility as both Dj and I had to make sure we were getting to the right place. For example, both of us have never been on the Millennium line which means we had to be responsible and make sure that we get off at the right stations and get onto the right sky train.

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Additional Resources to Support this Project

Felt Map: <https://felt.com/map/Future-Transit-Map-LadDJ6txTUizgONcRhdbZA?loc=49.1747,-122.878,9.79z&classId=dc0adcbb-942e-4399-96d7-15dbd8868488&assignmentId=228e3e90-1ae9-43e4-b862-8edf35550ef7&submissionId=409bcd92-8cf5-4bcb-d2d6-f91bd9ea5fa0>